

Skills Needed for Operating Tungsten Inert Gas Welding in Small and Medium Scale Welding Shops in Kaduna State

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Abstract

This study investigated and identified skills needed for operating tungsten inert gas (TIG) welding in small and medium scale welding shops in Kaduna state. The main objective was to determine the TIG welding technical skills needed for operating small and medium scale welding shop. A survey research design was adopted. The population for the study was 35. The population was made up of 12 welding teachers and 23 TIG welding operator. Sampling was not necessary due to relative smallness of the population. The findings revealed 47 TIG welding skills as the needed skills for successful operation of small scale TIG welding shop. amongst these identified skills, Cleaning of base metals, edge preparation and Precise control of welding torch are critical in the production of strong, clean and dependable welds. The study concludes that TIG welding operators have to acquire these skills through strategies like apprenticeship and certification programmes. Recommendations were made among which it was recommended that, small scale TIG welding shop operator must strive to acquire TIG welding technical skills so that they can effectively produce strong and reliable weld while they remain safe from hazards of TIG welding process.

Key words: TIG-welding, Skills, welding-shop

Background of the Study

Operators of small-scale welding shop do not possess adequate Tungsten Inert Gas (TIG) Welding skills for operating small scale shop. TIG welding is a welding process that permanently joins metals by localized coalescence through the application of heat obtained between a work piece and an arc that is produced by a non-consumable tungsten electrode. Larry, Lawrence and Hugh (2013), defined TIG welding as a welding process that uses an arc that is established between a non-consumable tungsten electrode and a work piece in the presence of an inert gas as a shielding gas. This welding process also utilizes argon gas or a mix of nonreactive gas depending on the metal being welded, as a shield against oxygen and nitrogen in the surrounding air. When metals get heated, they become excited and thus readily react with substances like oxygen and nitrogen in the air (Larry et al, 2013), this reaction is known as oxidation, oxidation make metals to become brittle and porous hence they are weakened to a point that they can structurally fail or become incapable of the service required of them. Inert gas is use as a shielding medium to prevent oxidation of the metal from taking place under heat. If the right amount of inert gas is delivered at the right time and location, the correct weld strength may be achieved when the foregoing is combined with the right skills. These skills that are considered to be the right skills are termed TIG welding technical skills.

TIG welding technical skills are proficiencies in manipulation of TIG welding machine and its accessories to correctly join metals permanently. A learner of skills usually becomes proficient in the skills being acquired through training and practice. Frederick and Christine (2017) refer to skills as the level of performance of an individual on a particular task or the capability to perform a job well. TIG welding operator need to perform TIG welds well while observing the requisite safety rules.

Safety rules are set of instruction or guide that are to be followed strictly to ensure that the operator is safe and free from effect of all potential hazards, safety skills are very important if

welding operator must be successful. A TIG welding operator must understand that identification of hazards and finding a way to work without suffering the negative effect of hazards is key in safe

welding. Hence the fore going statement can be interpreted as portraying welding as a dangerous occupation. welding is indeed a dangerous occupation because a welding operator is exposed to hazards like electric shock, Ultra Violet and Infra-red ray, fire/ heat and sometimes heights as well as trip hazards.

Ultraviolet (UV) ray is that bright visible ray that is emitted from an arc as arc (TIG) welding progresses, this ray was defined by Samir, Najla, Yasin and Maqboula (2022) as a type of electromagnetic radiation that makes black-light posters glow, However, too much exposure to UV radiation is damaging to living tissue. Tissues of the eye and cells of human skin are easily damaged by this ray, particularly, this ray can cause arc eye if the eye is not properly protected and the operator may suffer burnt skin if the skin is not properly protected from this ray (Samir et al 2022). Thus, a skilled welding operator should know how to protect their eyes and skin again this damaging ray. Another ray of concern in welding is infrared ray. infra-red ray is the red-hot heat emitted by molten metal. according to Hokmabadi, Taeebi and Fallah, (2019), Infrared Ray (IR) is a type of electromagnetic radiation having wave length longer than visible light but shorter than microwave. This ray is not visible by human eyes but humans feel them as heat. Infrared ray may not be as dangerous as ultra violet ray but, it has the potency of causing discomfort in the eyes and burning effect on the skin. Apart from potential damaging effect of infrared ray, welding operators should understand that they are also exposed to potential electric shock as a hazard.

Electric shock is usually a reaction by human muscles which happens when a certain amount of electricity passes through the human body. Electric shock can range from tingling sensation to a heavy involuntary muscular movement and even death. Death usually occurs when the electricity entering the body is strong enough to stop the heart muscles from pumping blood. Abiodun, Kehinde, Samson, Mathew and Abimbola (2024), saw electric shock as the passage of

electric current through human cells, which may lead to mild or severe discomfort, health concerns, or even electrocution. Electrocution could men death by passage of electric current through a living being, as such, welding operators must acquire skills in protecting themselves from electrocution or discomfort associated with misuse of electricity while welding. In the course of serving as welding operator, there may be need to work at heights and to move around work pieces.

Working at heights entails carrying out welding operation at locations that are above the ground. When working above the ground the welding operator will surely require scaffolds like ladder. Working at height exposes the welding operator to risk of falling off at height and hence the welding operator is expected to possess the skill to safely work at height. In the same breath a welding operator also moves around work pieces especially when doing out of position welding like 5G and 6G welding. In carrying-out out of position welding, a welding operator can trip and fall. Tripping and falling is a source of injury and possible fatality that must be avoided in the course of TIG welding hence a welding operation should be an expert in ensuring that their work environment is free of obstacle that can result in tripping and falling. When a TIG welding operator can safely weld then such a welding operator can focus on quality welds. Achieving a quality weld requires the TIG welding operator to possess technical skills, manual dexterity and focus on details apart from knowledge of safety rules earlier discussed.

Technical skills in the context of TIG welding are the possession of abilities and understanding of TIG welding equipment. It is knowing how to set up and adjust the welding machine to obtain the correct amperage, shielding gas flow rate and selection of the correct tungsten electrode as well as filler rod if required. For a welding operator to be able to select the correct tungsten electrode and maybe filler rod, the operator must be knowledgeable in the types and qualities of tungsten electrodes available as well as the types and quality of filler rods available. Welding operator should also possess the knowledge and understanding of metals and their properties as part of technical skill (Frederick & Christine, 2017). A welding operator should understand how different metals behave under heat in certain environment. A technically skilled

TIG welding operator should be able to control an electric arc to maintain an acceptable arc length. Control has to do with Manual dexterity or skill.

Manual skill is the capacity to effectively and productively coordinate the hands, eye, legs and the whole-body movement to achieve a desired result. To effectively weld, hand and eye coordination is essential (Zainul, Romi, Willadi, Arie, Oktarifaldi and syahrial, 2019). As TIG welding requires the use of both hands (one hand holds the torch and the other hand holds and feeds the filler rod), both hands must be as steady as they can be while maintaining a smooth travel along the joint. As a TIG welding operator welds, the operator needs to pay attention to details.

Details like weld appearance, signs of porosity, overheating and contamination. Paying attention to the details mentioned above is simply an effort aimed at avoiding the occurrence of defects.

Defects are flaws or imperfection that occur in a weld that renders the weld unattractive or weak for the purpose it is designed. Defects that are likely occur when welding by means of a TIG welding machine as identified by Saadat and Wajahat (2019) include internal porosity, undercut, lack of fusion, lack of penetration, excessive penetration, inclusion, cracks and crater cracks as well as underfill, surface porosity, spatters, arc strike and so on. Saadat and Wajahat (2019) went further to broadly classify TIG weld defects into internal defects and external defects. Whether a weld defect is external or internal, it cannot be accepted, as it is a source of failure of the article welded, hence when producing article in a TIG welding shop, defects must be avoided at all cost. If defective weld pass without detection, they are a source of hazard like accidents as a result equipment failure which can be costly repair; accidents as a result of defective weld can result in injuries to operators and even dead, hence, a TIG welding shop must guard against occurrence defect.

A TIG welding shop is a facility or a space where metal joining by means of application of heat using a tungsten inert gas welding equipment is carried out. Welding operator can on their own operate such shop as a source or means of earning a lively hood. When a TIG welding operator

establishes a TIG welding shop, such a welding shop is seen as a small scale TIG welding shop and can be successfully operated only when the operator possesses TIG welding technical skills.

It is these needed TIG welding technical skills that this study sought to identify so as to provide TIG welding operators with information about skills and strategies for acquiring these needed skills that are critical in effective operation of their shop as well as provide academics with an empirical evidence and body of knowledge of how these needed TIG welding technical skills were identified while filling the gap of absence of empirical studies in this branch of knowledge.

Statement of the Problem

Tungsten inert gas (TIG) welding is one of the many arc welding processes. it a welding process that can guarantee clean and effect joint in sheet metal and metal that are relatively thin like metals used in building vehicle bodies, but the concern is that most small-scale welding

operators like panel beaters and metal fabricators do not use TIG welding equipment in their welding operation and this is partly due to inadequate TIG welding technical skills. This study therefore sets out to identify the needed TIG welding skills for successful operation of a TIG welding shop so that welding operator can acquire these skills and become proficient in the use of TIG welding equipment in their small-scale welding shop.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study is to determine the TIG welding technical skills needed for operating small scale welding shop, specifically the study sought to identify

1. The TIG welding technical skills needed by TIG welding operator for operating a small-scale welding shop
2. The strategies for acquiring TIG welding skills

Research Questions

The following research question were raised to guide the study and answered to meet the purpose of the study.

1. What are the TIG welding technical skills needed by TIG welding operators to operate a small-scale welding shop?
2. What are the strategies for acquiring TIG welding technical skills?

Methodology

Survey research design was used for the study. According Auwal (2020), Survey research design is the most suitable research design when opinions of respondents are been sought. The study was conducted in Kaduna state. There are six technical colleges in the state where welding teachers were found. Twenty-three (23) welding shop where TIG welding is practiced was also located in Kaduna state.

The population for the study was thirty-five (35) which was made up of twelve (12) fabrication and welding teachers and twenty-three TIG welding operators. The population of the welding teachers was obtained from Kaduna state science and technical school management board

while the population of the TIG welding operators was obtained through snow balling. There was no need for sampling as the population was relatively small and manageable.

A researcher made questionnaire was the instrument for data collection and this instrument was titled TIG Welding Skills Needed for operating small scale Welding shop (TIWSNOSW). This instrument was developed based on a careful review of related literature. The instrument was made of four sections (section A to C). Section A covers 3 general questions while the other two sections were organized such that the respondent express their opinion on a four-point scale as Highly Needed (HN; 3.50 to 4.0), Needed (N; 2.5 to 3.49), Really Needed (RN; 1.50 to 2.49) and Not Needed (NN; 1.00 to 1.49). Each of the sections (section B to C) contains items that a response to them base on the four-point scale will lead to answering research question 1 and 2.

The data collected was analyzed using descriptive statistic. Mean was used to determine the extent of need. The mean of each item was interpreted in relation to real limit of numbers or the value assigned to the response category. Standard deviation was used to determine how the responses were closely spread or widely spread around the mean.

Results

Research question 1

What are the TIG welding technical skills needed by TIG welding operators to operate a small-scale welding shop?

**Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of the Responses of welding teachers and TIG welding shop operators on TIG welding skills needed to operate a TIG welding shop
N = 35**

S/N	TIG welding technical skills should include, ability to:	\bar{X}	S.D	Remark
1	Clean base metals	3.51	0.54	Highly Needed
2	Prepare edges of base metals thicker than 6mm	3.35	0.52	Needed
3	Precisely control welding torch	3.42	0.57	Needed
4	Effectively tack weld	3.26	0.67	Needed
5	Flip base metal for tack welding on its other side	3.39	0.65	Needed
6	Blend tack welds into the weld	3.37	0.64	Needed
7	Select the suitable welding current based on electrode type	3.32	0.66	Needed
8	Select TIG electrode based on metal to be welded	3.44	0.71	Needed
9	Strike an arc and sustaining the arc	3.35	0.61	Needed
10	Know the right arc length	3.33	0.66	Needed
11	Make a root pass	3.47	0.54	Needed
12	Clean a root pass	3.37	0.52	Needed
13	Make subsequent passes	3.32	0.54	Needed
14	Weld within full length of joint	3.28	0.59	Needed
15	Produce a weld having adequate penetration	3.19	0.69	Needed
16	Smoothly restart and arc after a stop	3.28	0.59	Needed
17	Produce a weld surface free of cracks	3.30	0.60	Needed
18	Produce a weld free of porosity	3.30	0.53	Needed
19	Produce a weld free of shrinkage cavity	3.25	0.63	Needed
20	Produce a weld free of stray arc marks	3.39	0.56	Needed
21	Produce a weld edge free of under cut	3.51	0.50	Highly Needed
22	Smoothly feed in a filler rod in weld pool	3.46	0.60	Needed
23	Maintain the right torch angle	3.40	0.59	Needed
24	Maintain the right travel speed	3.46	0.60	Needed
25	Prevent the occurrence of weld defects	3.44	0.57	Needed
26	Achieve proper bead profile	3.47	0.36	Needed
27	To initiate an arc	3.63	0.52	Highly Needed
29	Maintain and arc	3.32	0.57	Needed
30	Control arc heat	3.33	0.61	Needed
31	Select the right shielding gas flow rate	3.23	0.68	Needed
32	Choosing the correct type of shielding gas	3.65	0.55	Highly Needed
33	Weld in flat position	3.51	0.50	Highly Needed
34	Weld in horizontal position	3.44	0.71	Needed
35	Welding in vertical position	3.30	0.60	Needed
36	Weld in overhead position	3.23	0.68	Needed
37	Carryout 5G welding	3.30	0.82	Needed
38	Carryout 6G welding	3.35	0.58	Needed
39	Carryout 6GR welding	3.51	0.50	Highly Needed
40	Comprehend welding symbols	3.60	0.56	Highly Needed
41	Always use personal protective equipment	3.61	0.53	Highly Needed
42	Protect their eyes from ultraviolet ray	3.58	0.60	Highly Needed
43	Protect their skin from harmful radiations	3.51	0.50	Highly Needed
45	Tig-weld metals based on their known properties	3.74	0.48	Highly Needed
46	Follow safety rules	3.65	0.55	Highly Needed

The result presented in Table 1 reveals that the means of the responses ranged from 3.23 to 3.74. All means fall within the real limits of “Highly needed” and “Needed” (3.50 to 4.00 and

2.50-3.49). This suggest that, the respondents agreed that all the items are TIG welding technical skills that are needed to operate a small-scale welding shop. The standard deviation also ranged from 0.50 to 0.82. this suggest that respondent’s opinions are averagely close to each other; they did not deviate from each other significantly except for item 37 on the table where the deviation is approaching unity (0.82). item 37 is ‘TIG welding skill should include the ability to carry out 5G welding’. On this item the deviation is moderate, showing that the respondent’s opinions are more varied but the mean strongly shows they agree that the skill is needed to effectively operate a TIG welding shop.

Research Question 2

What are the strategies for acquiring TIG welding technical skills?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of the Responses of welding teachers and TIG welding shop operators on strategies for acquiring TIG welding skills

N = 35

S/N	Strategies for acquiring TIG welding skill should include:	\bar{X}	S.D	Remark
1	TIG welding certification programmes	3.51	0.50	Highly Needed
2	TIG welding Apprenticeship programmes	3.25	0.63	Needed
3	TIG welding workshop programmes	3.42	0.57	Needed
4	Practicing TIG welding skills under a mentor	3.26	0.67	Needed
5	Continued learning and adaptation of TIG welding skills	3.40	0.59	Needed
6	Networking and learning TIG welding skills from expert pears	3.37	0.64	Needed
7	Reading practical books and practicing TIG welding skills	3.32	0.66	Needed
8	Using You tube to practice and acquire TIG welding skills	3.25	0.63	Needed

The result presented in Table 2 reveals that the means of the responses ranged from 3.25 to 3.51. All means fall within the real limits of “Highly needed” and “Needed” (3.50 to 4.00 and 2.50-3.49). This suggest that, the respondents agreed that all the items are needed strategies for acquiring the needed skills for operating a small and medium scale welding shop.

The standard deviation also ranged from 0.50 to 0.67. this suggest that respondent's opinions are averagely close to each other; they did not deviate from each other significantly hence it can be concluded that the respondents are in agreement that all items on table 2 are the strategies for acquiring TIG welding technical skills for effective operation of TIG welding shop.

Findings

From the analyzed data, 47 (forty-seven) TIG welding technical skills have been identified as needed by operators of small and medium scale TIG welding shop and 8 (eight) strategies for acquiring TIG welding technical skills were identified. Out of the 47 identified TIG welding technical skills 12 (twelve) skills are highly needed while 35 (thirty-five) technical skills were needed. Similarly, out of the 8 (eight) strategies identified as needed strategies for acquiring TIG welding technical skills one strategy (TIG welding certification Programme) is highly needed as a strategy for acquiring TIG welding technical skills while the other six strategies are just needed strategies for acquiring TIG welding technical skills.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study have been arranged and discussed according to the two research questions. The finding that 47 TIG welding technical skills are needed for operating a TIG welding shop is supported by Dimkpa, Ikenyiri & Nkinebari, (2025), where they reported that technical skills are the bed rock of success in vocational technical education. TIG welding technical skills like Cleaning of base metals, edge preparation and Precise control of welding torch are critical in the production of strong, clean and dependable welds, no wonder the welding teachers and welding operators viewed these skills as needed for operating a welding shop.

Investigation by Pritesh and Vishvesh (2017), found out that cleaning of base metals before carrying out TIG welding guarantees a weld with little or no contaminant and that, adequate edge preparation coupled with precise torch control will no doubt result in a strong reliable weld. Another set of TIG welding technical skills for operating TIG welding shop as found out by this study include ability to select the correct welding current, ability to select correct electrode and understanding of base metal properties and behaviour under the influence of heat. For example, aluminum usually forms an oxide layer that is protective to its internal structure but this oxide film or layer has a melting point that is three times higher than internal structure of the aluminum and this property makes aluminum a special metal to weld (Prakasham, Siva, Naveen & Sheshu, 2018). The foregoing suggests that aluminum and its alloys must be welded using alternating current

mode on a TIG welding machine as alternating current has the ability to remove this tough oxide film and produce a strong weld that otherwise will be weak and brittle. Hence selection of the right welding current is key in producing a strong weld, but an absolute strong weld is only possible if the correct electrode is selected, a correct electrode refers to an electrode that will guarantee focusing of the welding arc and minimal erosion of electrode tip. Prakasham et al (2018) earlier confirmed this assertion when they reported that an eroded electrode tip will cause arc to lack focus hence the welding arc may be directed to the wrong spot and this can lead to defects like lack of fusion, lack of penetration and undercut.

Welding position found to be needed for operating a TIG welding shop is actually critical in TIG welding, this is because, before a weld is made, the welding operator must be in close proximity with the job, the job could be overhead relative to the welding operator, vertical, horizontal or flat relative to the operator's standing. Some jobs could be adjusted or moved to suit the operators desired position while in some cases, the operator has to angle themselves to be able to weld as the job is fixed, this therefore necessitates the need for TIG welding operators to master welding in all positions so that they expertly weld any job that comes their way. In the course of

welding, the operator is usually exposed to hazards and for this reason, welding has been classified as a dangerous operation as such welding operators must always protect themselves from the dangers associated with welding.

This study found out that TIG welding operators need to protect their eyes and body against infrared ray and ultraviolet ray as these rays have the potency to cause arc eye, skin cancer and burns. In view of the foregoing Hokmabadi et al (2019) strongly suggest that, TIG welding operator can protect against these hazards by wearing personal protective equipment like google, face shield, welding helmet, leather hand glove/gauntlets, safety boots and coverall as well as leather apron. While this study reinforces the need for welding operators to adequately protect themselves against all safety concerns when welding, it made effort to identify strategies for acquiring TIG welding technical skills which include operation skills and safety skills.

This study found out that TIG welding technical skill can be acquired through TIG welding certification programmes and apprenticeship. While certification programmes are usually offered by welding professional bodies, apprenticeship is generally offered by master craftsman. Welding professional bodies often organize short courses for prospective welding operator or welding operators who want to improve their skills. The welding professional bodies achieve their objective by delivering theoretical and practical lessons such that the trainees complete the programme by gaining both theoretical knowledge and practical skills for effective welding. This finding agrees with Donald (2023) as he reported that certification validates and improves welding operator's competencies. In the same breath apprenticeship been a programme where the trainee gains knowledge and skill by observing and imitating a master craftsman, is a suitable way to acquire TIG welding skill this is supported by Gessler, (2019) as he reported that apprenticeship is an interface between work and learning where knowledge and skills are acquired first hand. This discussion shows that TIG welding technical skills can be effectively acquire through apprenticeship.

Other strategies that can guarantee acquisition of TIG welding technical skills as found out by this study includes TIG welding workshop programmes, Practicing TIG welding skills under a mentor, continued learning and adaptation of TIG welding skills, networking and learning TIG welding skills from expert peers, reading practical books and practicing TIG welding skills and usage of you tube to acquire TIG welding skills. These strategies can be seen as short courses and short courses have proven to be effective means of acquiring knowledge and skills when training is to last for a relatively short period. This is true as elaborated by Ato and Ato (2018) where they have it that short-term training sessions have enabled trainees to grow as professionals on top of enabling them to acquire knowledge and skills that can directly be applied to the job they are doing.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study sets out to identify skills needed for operating TIG welding in small and medium scale welding shops in Kaduna state. The findings revealed that 47 technical skills are needed by operators of small scale TIG welding shop. Among these identified skills, skills like Cleaning of base metals, edge preparation and Precise control of welding torch are critical in the production of strong, clean and dependable welds, while skills like ability to protect

the eyes, skin and the entire body from dangerous ray, heat/burns and injuries are significant for continue operation. The findings strongly suggest that welding operators have to acquire these skills through strategies like apprenticeship and certification programmes. However, the study was limited to a relatively small population which was studied in its entirety and this small population size (sample size) may affect the generalizability of the findings. In orders to improve the potential for generalizability of the study, further research should be carried out to cover Nigeria as the area of the study so as to have a larger population. Ultimately this study contributes to the expanding need for empirical evidence concerning skills needed for successful operation of small and medium scale TIG welding shop.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendation were made:

1. Small and medium scale TIG welding shop operator must strive to acquire TIG welding technical skill so that they can effectively produce strong and reliable weld while they remain safe from hazards of TIG welding process. They can acquire TIG welding technical skills by enrolling in TIG welding apprenticeship programmes, certification programmes, continued learning and adaptation of TIG welding skills and the like.
2. The teachers of welding in schools and colleges through their supervisory bodies should strive to include TIG welding technical skills in their curriculum and as well teach the trainees these skills so that the trainees of their programme can graduate possessing TIG welding skills.

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